

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF REBRANDING STRATEGIES ON BRAND LOYALTY IN COMPETITIVE MARKETS: A CONSUMER RETENTION PERSPECTIVE

VARUN JEWARGI

Faculty of MBA Department, Jain College of Engineering, Visvesvaraya Technological University, Belagavi, India. Email: varun.jewargi@gmail.com, ORCID ID- 0000-0003-4073-9275

Dr. VEERENDRAKUMAR M NARASALAGI

Faculty of MBA Department, Dr. P.G. Halakatti College of Engineering and Technology, Visvesvaraya Technological University, Vijayapur, India. Email: veerumn@gmail.com, ORCID ID- 0000-0002-2819-7912

Dr. SHIVASHANKAR K

Faculty of MBA Department, Davangere University, Davangere, India.
Email: shivashankarabm@gmail.com, ORCID ID- 0000-0002-6318-1481

Abstract

The focus of this research is to gain insight into brand loyalty after rebranding literature by investigating: (a) the comparative change in customer trust for a brand; (b) the comparative change in customer brand commitment; (c) the comparative change in attitudinal and behavioural loyalty of the customers towards the brand after the change in the brand name. We have checked the customers loyalty towards the brand after the name change. The study makes a unique contribution by segmenting loyalty into attitudinal and behavioural forms. Survey methodology is employed to gather responses from 1137 Glow & Lovely face cream customers. Data is collected through a structured questionnaire with statements rated on a 7-point Likert scale. Convenience sampling is utilized, and the data analysis is conducted using Partial Least Square (PLS) 4.0.9.9. The key objective of the research is to offer comprehensive information regarding the customers loyalty after rebranding.

Keywords: Face Cream, Brand Trust, Brand Commitment, Attitudinal Loyalty and Behavioural Loyalty.

1. INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly modest atmosphere, a brand appears as the greatest appreciated, premeditated, critical advantage for a company, harvesting noteworthy consideration. According to (Keller, 1993) a well-known brand helps customers build a mental brand structure, of which the name, logo, and color outline may be a part. The marketers keep on changing their brand name as it is an old practice in the market this is mostly done to safeguard the equity of the product (Muzellec and Lambkin 2006).

Since the equity of the company is based on the history of the company, rebranding aimed at altering the characteristics of a brand may also cause dissonance in this situation (Aaker and Joachimsthaler 2000; Keller and Lehmann, 2006).

If you look into the history of rebranding in India by considering the examples of companies like Glod Spot which renamed to Fanta after being acquired by Coca-Cola, Wimco was renamed to ITC Limited, reliance Infocom to Reliance Jio, Hutchison Max Telecom to Vodafone idea, Standard Chartered bank to Standard Chartered plc and the

same with Fair & Lovely to Glow and Lovely by Unilever. Brand loyalty is a commonly deliberated notion in marketing literature, a portrayal courtesy from both researchers and consultants who are intense on effectually managing it (Techawachirakul, 2020).

It is a primary tool for vendors to alleviate buyers' price kindness in the market race (Helmig, Huber and Leeflang, 2007). Consumers are persuaded to recompense a first-class for a brand after they remark extraordinary price that no competitor can contest (Jacoby, Chestnut and Fisher, 1978). Therefore, brand executives struggle to address this test by cultivating stronger brands (Keller, 1993). Numerous revisions have discovered the connection between brand trust, brand commitment, and loyalty (Crespo-Almendros et al. 2022).

In such a situation it is very much necessary to investigate the influence of rebranding on customer's trust and commitment to the brand. According to (Keller, 1993) rebranding is more of brand upgrading, rebranding can help the customers improve the brand image in the thoughts of the patrons at the same time they can gain more loyalty of the customers.

It can be possible only through better improvement of the brand by creating new identity with the existing (Keller, 1993) it can also create positive impact for the brand (Downs and Haynes, 1984). After that you could measure if a high equity brand gains more to rebrand or a low equity brand will lose the most by having their current brand renamed (Roy and Sarkar 2015).

The allure of the Face care industry has prompted companies to adopt brand extension strategies, addressing the challenges posed by the intensely competitive skincare market. The primary function of a brand is to distinguish these offerings since contending belongings or facilities, as emphasized by (Keller and Lehmann 2006). In the beginning of 2019, the brand's messaging shifted from emphasizing fairness, lightening, and skin whitening to focus on glow, even tone, skin clearness, and warmth — holistic indicators of healthy skin.

According to (Jewargi, Narasalagi and Saraih 2022) nowadays, there is a large need for cosmetic products in the market. This evolution is captured in the new name 'Glow & Lovely,' aligning with a more wide-ranging vision of beauty. (<https://www.hul.co.in>). On July 2nd 2020 Unilever rebranded the name Fair & Lovely to Glow and Lovely. (<https://www.forbes.com>). This perspective underscores the pivotal role of branding as a decisive factor for companies seeking to reinforce their position in the Facecare category.

Brand loyalty entails consumers being willing to recompense premium prices for a precise brand within similar product category and recommending that brand to others. Descriptive studies that offer standards and benchmarks for cross-category loyalty measurements are scarce (Mundt, Dawes and Sharp 2006).

Brand trust and loyalty are both decisive theories in the arena of marketing. brand trust discusses to a customer's self-assurance in product's capability to distribute on the possibilities, while brand loyalty mentions to a customer's frequent buying behaviour towards an explicit brand. Numerous research has inspected the relation amid trust and

loyalty, it has stood initiated that trust has a substantial power on brand loyalty (Ali et al. 2021). Nevertheless, the abundance of brands offering similar products within the market makes it easy for consumers to switch brands, posing a challenge to the establishment of brand loyalty (Wood, 2004).

Administrators and scholars are beginning to focus more on this issue as loyalty gets harder and harder to cultivate. According to (Hwang et al., 2021). Customers should find a brand to be emotionally appealing. Notably, the second most important factor influencing brand satisfaction is an impactful brand experience. Attitude and behavioural characteristics are used extensively in marketing literature to quantify customer loyalty (Ganesh, 2000; Han, Kim and Kim 2011).

According to (Chaudhuri and Holbrook, 2002) attitudinal loyalty includes commitment, favourable word of mouth, and a declared intention to buy, whereas behavioural loyalty includes the likelihood of repeat purchases, exclusive purchases, and a knowledge of category requirements. Satisfied customers tend to demonstrate commitment by continuously choosing and remaining loyal to the same brand (Ballantyne, Warren and Nobbs 2006). However, satisfaction alone is not adequate for creating brand loyalty.

The main aim is to ascertain how the name change of face cream has impacted consumer loyalty. (a) the comparative change in customer trust for a brand; (b) the comparative change in customer brand commitment; (c) the comparative change and relationship between attitudinal and behavioural loyalty of the customers towards the brand after the change in the brand name.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

The term brand is widely recognized across diverse audiences, encompassing both laypeople and researchers specializing in this concept. In marketing, the idea of brand loyalty is essential according to (Tellis 2018). A faithful customer is further expected to endorse the brand to others, plummeting price of obtaining novel clients. Furthermore, loyalty improves a firm's reputation, which can chief to amplified marketplace stake and diversity from players (Maheshwari, Lodorfos and Jacobsen 2014). Establishing customer loyalty has become a key strategy for protecting market shares.

Firms with loyal customer bases ensure long-term sustainability by encouraging repeat purchases. As a result, numerous studies in the literature focus on exploring variables that influence brand loyalty. Customers exhibiting high brand loyalty are characterized by their consistent and repetitive purchases of a particular brand, coupled with a sturdy sagacity of commitment to that brand (Baldinger, 1996).

The commitment displayed by these customers transforms them into loyal patrons who consistently engage in recurrence buying. Redemption intents are commonly associated with brand commitment, yet it's crucial to distinguish between the two. It entails an affiliation parallel to alliance that consumers cultivate with a brand. On the other hand, repeat purchase is driven by factors such as cost-effectiveness or the absence of viable alternatives.

Brand Trust

H1: Brand trust is positively related to Attitudinal loyalty.

H2: Brand trust is positively related to Behavioural loyalty.

It is a pivotal concept in numerous revisions (Doney and Cannon, 1997). Its significance is often theorised as a key issue in the accomplishment of a firm (Morgan and Hunt, 1994). Consumer loyalty plays a very vital role in any business for brand to grow in the market (Oliver, 1999). Here we can observe that customer is delighted with the performance of the product, loyalty is just a way to tell their views about the product (Delgado-Ballester and Luis Munuera-Alemán, 2005).

According to (Buchanan 1974) commitment scale was used to check and measure the loyalty of the customers. It was basically how the humans measure the eagerness for their favourite brand. Brand trust is a notion prime to brand loyalty and dense purchaser product linkage, according to experimental suggestion. This is interrelated to trust competence to sustenance tremendously from top to toe appreciated product associations (Chaudhuri and Holbrook 2002).

As an outcome, loyalty can be well-thought-out constituent enduring progression of appreciated besides perceptible associations that trust yields (Frydman 2022). Additionally, it is asserted that strong emotional bonds and attachments between customers and brands grow as a result of bonding (Liu et al. 2017). According to (Rubio, Villaseñor and Yagüe 2017) price points, customer satisfaction, and the values that consumers perceive from a brand are all related to brand trust and loyalty.

Brand Commitment

H3: Brand commitment is positively related to Attitudinal loyalty.

H4: Brand commitment is positively related to Behavioural loyalty.

When the customer really likes the product, they will be committed towards the brand, but at the same time the marketer has to maintain the quality of the brand. The term brand commitment describes the persistent wish to stay in touch with the company's reputation (Chen and Myagmarsuren, 2011). Such a desire, as stated by (Morgan and Hunt, 1994) is essential to every relationship that the company has with its many partners. As proposed by (Morgan and Hunt, 1994) trust and commitment are indispensable fundamentals in edifice and preserving positive associations between customers and brands. Commitment, as defined by (Anon 2003), necessitates a long-lasting disposition to sustain a connexion with a brand.

When we consider brand loyalty commitment plays a vital role in it. Furthermore, instead of looking at customer satisfaction related to service consumption (Alnawas and Hemsley-Brown, 2018). Because it fosters exchange connections that are valued highly, brand trust promotes brand commitment (Morgan and Hunt, 1994). As we need to check the repeat purchase of the customer attachment and belief towards the products. So, the marketer has to build a strong emotional bondage among the customers.

In studies examining the influence of brand trust on brand commitment, (Shergill and Li, 2005) found a positive effect, indicating that trust will have a noteworthy protagonist in fostering customer assurance. Study has confirmed that trust and commitment suggestively stimulus brand loyalty (Suhan et al. 2022). Patrons who belief dedicated to a product are additional probable to occupy in optimistic behaviours such as recurrence acquisitions, encouraging confrontation to inexpensive contributions (Kaur and Soch 2018). Commitment trust concept climaxes the critical part of brand trust and commitment in construction, preserving durable relations between clients and products.

Attitudinal loyalty and Behavioural loyalty

H5: Attitudinal loyalty is positively related to Behavioural loyalty.

Many researchers who have worked on the customer loyalty concept of attitudinal loyalty and behavioural loyalty (Jacoby et al. 1978; Mano and Oliver 1993). Much of the literature, according to (Kim 2024) a strong commitment to sticking with the same supplier that results in repeat business is implied by loyalty. According to Thomson et al. (2014), emotional brand attachment is a bond that is filled with feelings of affection and connection between a person and a brand.

This bond encourages customers to repurchase and demonstrate commitment (Athanasopoulou, 2018). Hence, emotional attachment and attitudinal loyalty are derived from the purchaser's observations of excellence, value, satisfaction, affection, and taste (Grisaffe and Nguyen, 2011). A more accurate measure of a customer's loyalty is the proportion of times they select a specific brand over alternatives (Tanford 2013). However, if a buyer has positive image toward a brand may not always guarantee repeat business or frequency of purchases (Dick and Basu 1994). According to (Izogo, 2015) attitudinal loyalty indicates the possibility that customers will stay with a business. Accordingly, it is imperative that future studies take into account the behavioural as well as attitudinal components of loyalty to clients (Han et al. 2011).

The current study connects feelings of affection for face care products rather than emphasizing it as was done in earlier research (Martínez and Bosque, 2013). Customers are motivated to pay more by a psychological mechanism known as attitudinal loyalty (Casper Ferm and Thaichon, 2021). Whereas a key performance indicator will help in creating customers loyalty (Jiddi 2023). Numerous research work claim that factual loyalty occurs in a mixing of both attitudinal loyalty and behavioural loyalty scopes (Dick and Basu, 1994) and consequently, the sellers are recommended to generate factual loyalty by emerging both attitudinal and behavioural methods.

According to (Dick and Basu, 1994) model, behavioural loyalty can be understood as buyers' forged faithfulness in a technique to benefaction single brand solitary. In additional method, attitudinal loyalty outlines customers' dormant boldness by emotional add-on with optimistic purchasing intents to a supplier.

A significant portion of the research has solely used an attitudinal approach to assess customer loyalty; nonetheless, a shopper's positive judgement of a certain brand does

not guarantee repeat business or frequency of repurchases (Dick and Basu, 1994). As a primary area of focus, the majority of pertinent published studies have looked at the direct correlation between customer loyalty and trust (Guenzi, Georges and Pardo, 2009). (Choi and La 2013) for example, demonstrated the positive correlation between customer loyalty and perceived corporate social responsibility (CSR), which is carried out by customer trust across a range of service industry types. Therefore, it is imperative that behavioural and attitudinal dimensions of client loyalty be taken into account in future research (Han et al., 2011).

As opposed to prior industry research (Martínez and Rodríguez Del Bosque, 2013) which placed more focus on attitudinal loyalty, the current study connects the face care industry's behavioural loyalty. Behavioural loyalty describes customers' acquisition regularity (Jacoby et al., 1978) and obtaining categorization (Kahn, Kalwani, and Morrison 1986) with a certain product or business. Buyers' sturdy behavioural purposes cheer them to re-entr.

These come back to can be persuaded by torpor (Dowling 1997) or any additional stimulus that persuades them to buyback with one vendor over a period of time. The redemption due to expressive closeness, inactivity, habituation, and deal-chasing explanations requirements to be forward-thinking by confident involvements somewhat than ratifying impartial transactional marketing inducements (F. Nunes et al., 2013). It could assist in emerging customers' lucid and sentimental answers with a steady, which might be indispensable to bring the right purchaser charge in command to increase dominance over additional multinationals.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Measurement instrument

Given that emotional brand attachment is a bond filled with strong feelings between a shopper and a brand, the foremost purpose is to ascertain how the name change of face cream has impacted consumer loyalty. (a) the comparative change in customer trust for a brand; (b) the comparative change in customer brand commitment; (c) the comparative change and relationship between attitudinal and behavioural loyalty of the customers towards the brand after the change in the brand name. A conceptual model has been built for the same (Figure 1). For this study, five important cities in the Indian state of North Karnataka were selected based on particular demographic and geographical behaviours.

Sample design and data collection

In order to test the proposed research hypotheses, convenience sampling method was utilized the researchers collected the data from five major cities: Belagavi (Belgaum), Dharwad, Vijayapura (Bijapur), Ballari (Bellary) and Kalburgi (Gulbarga) in North Karnataka, India. The questionnaire was distributed through online and offline mode. The female customers between the age of 18 and 50 who are using the brand, only they were contacted out of 1500 questionnaires, 1137 were found to be accurately and totally completed.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for the Study

Product Selection

The research has chosen Glow & Lovely face cream as the focal product, motivated by various factors. Face creams enjoy widespread popularity among consumers in our vicinity, with almost everyone using a brand of face cream, resulting in a high level of cognizance and attention in this product. Here we wanted to check the loyalty of the customers after the rebranding as many customers thought that the product has changed or just the name. Moreover, face creams have become indispensable for consumers, particularly the younger demographic, due to the comfort they offer. Beyond functional advantages, these products also provide psychological benefits. Hence, in selecting these products, both brand trust and affective factors can play a significant role. In this context, the Glow & Lovely face cream brand is perceived as having the potential to influence consumers through both brand trust and brand commitment even after rebranding.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Scale validity and reliability

Using MS Excel for statistical computation and SmartPLS-4.0.9.9 (Ringle, Da Silva, and Bido 2014) for partial least square analysis using the Structural Equation Modeling technique, the suggested research structure of the current study was examined. Initially, the suggested study model and measures were estimated using the SmartPLS-4.0.9.9 program (Chin, Marcolin, and Newsted 2003). Additionally, this software measures the influence of every independent variable on the dependent variable and ascertains the constructs relationship with the dependent variable. Second, MS Excel was used to conduct the demographic analysis and estimate the importance of loadings of factors and path coefficients. This study adopts a quantitative approach, employing suitable statistical tools to explore relationships among the outlined variables. A Likert scale, ranging from one to seven points, is utilized in the survey to allow respondents to express their preferences. Sample size determination follows the hypothesis testing criteria for PLS,

utilizing resampling with Bootstrapping. Convenience sampling is employed, distributing questionnaires to users of specific face cream brands who happen to use the product by chance (Kriyantono 2012). This method aims to ensure that the sample represents a broad and diverse population.

Table 1: Details of the factors adopted for the study

Item	Author
Brand Trust	
This brand accomplishes my opportunities	
I observe this brand as truthful	(Delgado-Ballester and Luis Munuera-Alemán, 2005)
This brand has an innocent high-quality for routine	
I favour this brand as a harmless prime for use	
Brand commitment	
I get optimistic sensation when using my present brand	
Using my current brand brings me confidence	(Coulter, Price, and Feick, 2003)
Using my up-to-date brand brings me happiness	
I descend pleasure from using my current brand	
Attitudinal loyalty	
I would willingly indorse this brand to my friends	
I am a dedicated customer to my favourite brand	(Chaudhuri and Holbrook, 2002)
The product quality is not comparable to others	
I am willing to pay a premium for this brand	
Behavioural loyalty	
I anticipate to endure buying this brand	
I perceive the quality of my favourite brand to be superior to others	
Despite of conflicting evidence about my favourite brand, I would still pick to purchase it	(Chaudhuri and Holbrook 2002)
If my preferred brand is inaccessible in the store, I would vigorously seek it out somewhere else	

In the above (Table 1) we can see the details of the factors adopted for the study, we have considered four factors in which brand trust and brand commitment are considered as independent variable Attitudinal loyalty is considered as mediating variable and behavioural loyalty is considered as dependent variable. For the source of the questionnaire when we consider the sub questions of the above factors brand trust is referred from (Delgado-Ballester and Luis Munuera-Alemán 2005), whereas brand commitment is considered from (Coulter et al. 2003), when we take into consideration attitudinal loyalty and behavioural loyalty it is referred from (Chaudhuri and Holbrook 2002). As much study has been already done on the same by many researchers in the past, but the concern was none of the researcher has done a study on rebranding of the product specifically with Glow & Lovely after the company Unilever changed the brand name what was the impact on the customers and the company in India. We basically wanted to check the loyalty of the customers even after there is a change in the brand name by considered the above-mentioned factors. So we have referred to the factors which were already studied and tried to implement the same on the face care product as

it's a low involvement product so knowing the customers loyalty would be interesting as they might continue to be loyal for the brand after the name change, else they might have switched the brand. So, what was the major factor effecting for the loyalty has been checked in this study. This would also be helping the companies in future when they are considering about rebranding their product name logo or design.

Table 2: Demographic data of customers

Districts	Respondents	Demographics	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Belagavi (Belgaum)	337	Gender	Female	1137	100
Dharwad	274	Age	18-25	592	52
Vijayapura (Bijapur)	135		26-30	394	35
Ballari (Bellary)	194		31-45	123	11
Kalburgi (Gulbarga)	197		46-50	28	2
Total	1137	Education	12th	132	12
			UG	182	16
			PG	823	72
		Domicile	Urban	998	88
			Rural	139	12
		Occupation	Student	904	80
			Services	112	10
			Home maker	54	5
			Business	67	6
		Annual Spend on the brand	Less than ₹.300	134	12
			₹.300-₹.500	974	86
			₹.500-₹.700	14	1
			More than ₹.700	15	1

In the above (Table 2) we can see that the respondents selected from the districts of North karnataka region are Belagavi (Belgaum) 337, Dharwad 274, Vijayapura (Bijapur) 135, Ballari (Bellary) 194 and Kalburgi (Gulbarga) 197. When we talk about the age range of the respondents 18-25 there are 592 respondents, between 26-30 there are 394 respondents, 31-45 there are 123 respondents and between 46-50 there are 28 respondents. When we look into the education of the respondents all the respondents are educated and highest was PG with 823 respondents. Domicile of the respondents most of them are from urban area around 998 respondents. Students were on the highest number around 904. When we look into the annual spend of the respondents around 974 respondents spend between ₹.300-₹.500 annually on this brand. We utilized composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach's alpha to evaluate the study's dependability. The constructs needed good and acceptable Cronbach's alpha values, and the internal consistency of the constructs was adequate according to the CR values, which required to be greater than 0.70 (Sarstedt et al., 2019) and (Bagozzi and Yi 1988). (Table 3) & (Figure 2) demonstrates that all independent variables possess Cronbach's alpha values over 0.70, indicating the reliability of their internal consistency.

AVE provides both divergent and convergent validity in a reflective model. In a nutshell it reflects each latent factor's average communality (Garson 2016). An AVE of in excess of

0.5 demonstrates that the model is correct (Hock and Ringle 2010). Whenever the error variance surpasses the explained variance, the AVE is less than 0.5. All of the variables in (Table 3) have outstanding AVE values. With an AVE of 0.771, brand trust earns the highest AVE, while behavioural loyalty has the lowest AVE 0.669. The remaining variables also display acceptable values, such as brand commitment at 0.710 and attitudinal loyalty at 0.670.

Table 3: Construct and measurement items

Item	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	Factor Loading	Cronbach's alpha	CR	AVE
Brand Trust						
This brand accomplishes my opportunities. (BT1)	0.938	0.005	0.938	0.899	0.931	0.771
I observe this brand as truthful (BT2)	0.940	0.004	0.940			
This brand has an innocent high-quality for routine. (BT3)	0.850	0.010	0.851			
I favour this brand as a harmless prime for use. (BT4)	0.773	0.015	0.774			
Brand commitment						
I get optimistic sensation when using my present brand (BC1)	0.856	0.012	0.857	0.865	0.907	0.710
Using my current brand brings me confidence (BC2)	0.867	0.009	0.867			
Using my up-to-date brand brings me happiness (BC3)	0.778	0.018	0.779			
I descend pleasure from using my current brand (BC4)	0.866	0.009	0.866			
Attitudinal loyalty						
I would willingly indorse this brand to my friends (AL1)	0.823	0.011	0.823	0.836	0.891	0.670
I am a dedicated customer to my favourite brand. (AL2)	0.799	0.012	0.799			
The product quality is not comparable to others. (AL3)	0.835	0.010	0.835			
I am willing to pay a premium for this brand. (AL4)	0.817	0.012	0.818			
Behavioural loyalty						
I anticipate to endure buying this brand. (BL1)	0.807	0.015	0.807	0.838	0.890	0.669
I perceive the quality of my favourite brand to be superior to others. (BL2)	0.831	0.012	0.831			
Despite of conflicting evidence about my favourite brand, I would still pick to purchase it (BL3)	0.799	0.017	0.799			
If my preferred brand is inaccessible in the store, I would vigorously seek it out somewhere else. (BL4)	0.834	0.014	0.835			

The methodology used in the study is the PLS approach, and structural equations based on variance are estimated using the Smart-PLS version 4 tool. Vital validity testing is part of the first step. The square root of the AVE values is then compared with the latent variables in order to evaluate discriminant validity using the Fornell-Larcker criterion (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). More specifically, the square root of the AVE should be larger than its highest correlation with any other component, as per (Sarstedt et al., 2019). (Table 3) shows that for reflecting domains such as attitudinal loyalty, behavioural loyalty, brand trust, & brand commitment, the square root of AVE was greater than the comparable relationship with latent variables. It was crucial that these ideas had discriminant validity.

Table 4: Construct and measurement items

Construct	AL	BC	BL	BT
AL	0.819			
BC	0.504	0.843		
BL	0.305	-0.027	0.818	
BT	0.722	0.682	0.130	0.878

Structural model calculation

Later we performed Fornell-Larcker using smart PLS 4.0. Here we basically wanted to check the discriminant validity of a measurement model. It ensures that each construct in the model is distinct and measures a unique concept. Each item in the cross loading was meeting the threshold, the diagonal value in the corelation matrix was greater than the other values in the rows and the columns (Table 4). The construct may be unique from other components in the model if its diagonal value is, in fact, larger. If not, it can suggest that discriminant validity is lacking.

Figure 2: Results of the Structural Model (PLS-SEM)

Following that, the researcher calculated the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) and found that all of the variables met the criteria, as shown in (Table 5) below. Where the HTMT value

needs to be less than 0.9, per Heseler (2014). (Table 5) indicates that the value of the HTMT requirements are satisfied.

Table 5: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio

Items	AL	BC	BL	BT
AL				
BC	0.571			
BL	0.358	0.077		
BT	0.829	0.769	0.143	

Later we performed Cross loading (Table 6) for the collected data and all the values were meeting the requirement (Hair et al. 2012). All the values for the factors were more than 0.6 (Ringle et al. 2014).

Table 6: Cross loading values

	AL	BC	BL	BT
AL1	0.823	0.451	0.199	0.600
AL2	0.799	0.254	0.328	0.538
AL3	0.835	0.527	0.177	0.670
AL4	0.818	0.405	0.303	0.548
BC1	0.432	0.857	-0.031	0.609
BC2	0.462	0.867	0.013	0.608
BC3	0.283	0.779	-0.089	0.482
BC4	0.477	0.866	-0.012	0.581
BL1	0.204	-0.027	0.807	0.117
BL2	0.260	-0.086	0.831	0.117
BL3	0.205	0.012	0.799	0.062
BL4	0.304	0.024	0.835	0.118
BT1	0.647	0.633	0.110	0.938
BT2	0.653	0.637	0.113	0.940
BT3	0.663	0.543	0.159	0.851
BT4	0.563	0.586	0.065	0.774

Figure 3: Results of the Bootstrapping (PLS-SEM)

Hypothesis Testing

(Table 7) displays the results of the hypothesis testing. The bootstrapping results, which are displayed in (Figure 3), were obtained by conducting 5000 samplings in order to investigate the links between the constructs in the suggested study model. Finding the path coefficient values, which represent the proposed hypotheses' significance level, was the next stage in the inner model test. A 5% confidence level was used for the inaccuracy in this study. Three supported and two unsupported hypotheses can be inferred from the results of the computation of the five hypotheses based on the measurement results shown in (Table 7) below. Each of them has a strong enough influence to be supported, however H2 and H3 are not supported because their P-values (of 0.382 and 0.467, respectively) do not fulfil the standards (P-value <0.50) (Hair et al. 2012).

Table 7: Hypothesis Test

Items		Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Hypothesis
H1	BT -> AL	0.707	0.708	0.026	26.964	0.000	Accepted
H2	BT -> BL	-0.038	-0.038	0.043	0.874	0.382	Rejected
H3	BC -> AL	0.021	0.021	0.029	0.728	0.467	Rejected
H4	BC -> BL	-0.226	-0.227	0.039	5.805	0.000	Accepted
H5	AL -> BL	0.446	0.448	0.036	12.443	0.000	Accepted

Discussion and Conclusion

The results of this study largely align with the variable relationships identified in previous research. The impact of brand trust on both behavioural and attitudinal loyalty, as well as the influence of brand commitment on attitudinal loyalty, advises that customers' trust in a particular brand can affect their emotional responses and commitment to the brand. The relationships between brand trust and attitudinal loyalty, as well as brand commitment, indicate that customers' emotional preferences and commitment can have an impact on both dimensions of loyalty. A noteworthy aspect of this research study is the inspection of the connection between brand trust and attitudinal and behavioural loyalty, revealing that brand trust (H1) significantly influences attitudinal loyalty. When we look into the second hypothesis (H2) brand trust on behavioural loyalty is getting rejected as we can say that customers who are using glow and lovely face care products do not have direct impact on behavioural loyalty for the product.

When we look into the brand commitment on attitudinal loyalty (H3) is getting rejected as we can say that the customer who are using the brand do not have an attitudinal loyalty towards the brand. But at the same time when we look into brand commitment towards behavioural loyalty (H4) is accepted which is a good sign as the customers have a behavioural loyalty towards the brand and will continue to have the same even after the change in the brand name.

A favourable emotional and cognitive bond that a consumer has with an item or company is known as attitude loyalty. This covers elements such as preference, trust, and

contentment. Contrarily, behavioural loyalty refers to a customer's actual purchase patterns and consistent brand devotion. The last hypothesis in the study was attitudinal loyalty will it lead to behavioural loyalty (H5) (Evanschitzky et al., 2006). Here we can see that the hypothesis is getting accepted. We can say that the customers attitudinal loyalty, though there is the change in the name of the brand the customers loyalty to the brand has not changed.

Ultimately, the current study finds that, despite taking into account a few variables to examine behavioural and attitudinal loyalty, brand name changes do not directly or indirectly affect brand loyalty. The findings hold good with the previous research (Bandyopadhyay and Martell 2007; Dick and Basu 1994; Jaiswal and Niraj 2011). According to the study, even when a customer's perceived emotional attachment is largely constant, there may be changes in their brand loyalty depending on their age and economic level.

The study comes to the additional conclusion that the association between emotional attachment and the antecedents of brand trust, brand commitment and loyalty is moderated by differences in income. The results corroborated the findings of earlier investigations of (Saini and Singh 2020). As an outcome, consumers who demonstration a high level of connection with a company are more inclined to remain loyal than those who show a low level of involvement, particularly in conditions where brand trust is low. This indicates that customers in the highest income bracket have the largest proportion of brand loyalty, which is mostly influenced by brand trust. Even after a brand name change, the benefits to the brand continue to foster positive perceptions and brand loyalty. Thus, customers will view a brand more favourably than they will other competing brands if they have a positive perception of the brand, which fosters brand loyalty.

5. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

Through discussing different aspects of brand loyalty, this study also provides some theoretical insights. Firstly, the research validates the impact of brand trust on attitudinal loyalty on behavioural loyalty, and brand commitment on attitudinal loyalty and behavioural loyalty. Brand commitment did not significantly affect attitudinal loyalty, while brand trust did not significantly affect behavioural loyalty.

Second, when we considered other factors like brand trust significantly affected attitudinal loyalty at the same time brand commitment and attitudinal loyalty had a positive effect on behavioural loyalty.

As a result, the study's conclusions will help businesses develop their plans for creating enduring brand loyalty following a rebranding since they have established consumer trust. The customer who trusts the brand and have commitment will never think of switching the brand as they will remain loyal towards it. Thus, we can say that customers loyalty will not change even after there is a change in the brand name as the companies have to concentrate more on maintaining the same quality of the product so that the customers will continue to buy the same even though there is no change in the product. Company

has to concentrate on more on creating more awareness about the rebranding that only the name has changed and the product remains the same so that the customers will continue to buy the product and remain loyal towards the brand.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

The study focused on understanding the customers brand loyalty towards the face cream brand Glow & lovely. Despite all the efforts put in the research two hypothesis got rejected out of five. The study was limited only to North karnataka region with five districts. And the loyalty was based on rebranding of the face cream with attitudinal and behavioural loyalty. May be in future the researchers should aim at considering more factors like brand affect, brand image, and also consider hedonic, cognitive and symbolic image of the brand so that the study would be more deeper to understand the loyalty of the customers and know will the customers switch from the brand or not. Additional to that the researchers can go for considering high involvement. As our study was of low involvement products, so the study with luxury brands with high involvement products would be more interesting to know the loyalty of the customers will it be same or it differs.

Reference

- 1) Aaker, David A., and Erich Joachimsthaler. 2000. "The Brand Relationship Spectrum: The Key to the Brand Architecture Challenge." *California Management Review* 42(4):8–23. doi: 10.1177/000812560004200401.
- 2) Ali, Afzaal, Mehkar Sherwani, Adnan Ali, Zeeshan Ali, and Mariam Sherwani. 2021. "Investigating the Antecedents of Halal Brand Product Purchase Intention: An Empirical Investigation." *Journal of Islamic Marketing* 12(7):1339–62. doi: 10.1108/JIMA-03-2019-0063.
- 3) Alnawas, Ibrahim, and Jane Hemsley-Brown. 2018. "The Differential Effect of Cognitive and Emotional Elements of Experience Quality on the Customer-Service Provider's Relationship." *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management* 46(2):125–47. doi: 10.1108/IJRDM-03-2017-0058.
- 4) Anon. 2003. "The Impact of Customer Trust and Perception of Security Control on the Acceptance of Electronic Commerce." *International Journal of Electronic Commerce* 7(3):135–61. doi: 10.1080/10864415.2003.11044270.
- 5) Athanasopoulou, Pinelopi. 2018. "Department of Business Administration, University of West Attica, Egaleo Athens, Greece and Department of Business Administration, Hellenic Open University, Greece, And."
- 6) Bagozzi, Richard R., and Youjiae Yi. 1988. "On the Evaluation of Structural Equation Models."
- 7) Baldinger, Allan L. 1996. "Brand Loyalty: The Link Between Attitude And Behavior."
- 8) Ballantyne, Ronnie, Anne Warren, and Karinna Nobbs. 2006. "The Evolution of Brand Choice." *Journal of Brand Management* 13(4–5):339–52. doi: 10.1057/palgrave.bm.2540276.
- 9) Bandyopadhyay, Subir, and Michael Martell. 2007. "Does Attitudinal Loyalty Influence Behavioral Loyalty? A Theoretical and Empirical Study." *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* 14(1):35–44. doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2006.03.002.
- 10) Buchanan, Bruce. 1974. "Government Managers, Business Executives, and Organizational Commitment." *Public Administration Review* 34(4):339. doi: 10.2307/975244.

- 11) Casper Ferm, Lars-Erik, and Park Thaichon. 2021. "Customer Pre-Participatory Social Media Drivers and Their Influence on Attitudinal Loyalty within the Retail Banking Industry: A Multi-Group Analysis Utilizing Social Exchange Theory." *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* 61:102584. doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102584.
- 12) Chaudhuri, A., and M. B. Holbrook. 2002. "Product-Class Effects on Brand Commitment and Brand Outcomes: The Role of Brand Trust and Brand Affect." *Journal of Brand Management* 10(1):33–58. doi: 10.1057/palgrave.bm.2540100.
- 13) Chen, Ching-Fu, and Odonchimeg Myagmarsuren. 2011. "Brand Equity, Relationship Quality, Relationship Value, and Customer Loyalty: Evidence from the Telecommunications Services." *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence* 22(9):957–74. doi: 10.1080/14783363.2011.593872.
- 14) Chin, Wynne W., Barbara L. Marcolin, and Peter R. Newsted. 2003. "A Partial Least Squares Latent Variable Modeling Approach for Measuring Interaction Effects: Results from a Monte Carlo Simulation Study and an Electronic-Mail Emotion/Adoption Study." *Information Systems Research* 14(2):189–217. doi: 10.1287/isre.14.2.189.16018.
- 15) Choi, Beomjoon, and Suna La. 2013. "The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Customer Trust on the Restoration of Loyalty after Service Failure and Recovery." *Journal of Services Marketing* 27(3):223–33. doi: 10.1108/08876041311330717.
- 16) Coulter, Robin A., Linda L. Price, and Lawrence Feick. 2003. "Rethinking the Origins of Involvement and Brand Commitment: Insights from Postsocialist Central Europe." *Journal of Consumer Research* 30(2):151–69. doi: 10.1086/376809.
- 17) Crespo-Almendros, Esmeralda, M. Belén Prados-Peña, Lucia Porcu, and Juan Miguel Alcántara-Pilar. 2022. "Influence of the Perceived Benefit of a Social Network-Based Sales Promotion on the Perceived Quality of a Heritage Complex." *Academia Revista Latinoamericana de Administración* 35(2):148–62. doi: 10.1108/ARLA-06-2021-0126.
- 18) Delgado-Ballester, Elena, and José Luis Munuera-Alemán. 2005. "Does Brand Trust Matter to Brand Equity?" *Journal of Product & Brand Management* 14(3):187–96. doi: 10.1108/10610420510601058.
- 19) Dick, A. S., and K. Basu. 1994. "Customer Loyalty: Toward an Integrated Conceptual Framework." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* 22(2):99–113. doi: 10.1177/0092070394222001.
- 20) Doney, Patricia M., and Joseph P. Cannon. 1997. "An Examination of the Nature of Trust in Buyer–Seller Relationships."
- 21) Dowling, Grahame R. 1997. "Do Customer Loyalty Programs Really Work?"
- 22) Downs, Phillip E., and Joel B. Haynes. 1984. "Examining Retail Image before and after a Repositioning Strategy."
- 23) Evanschitzky, Heiner, Gopalkrishnan R. Iyer, Hilke Plassmann, Joerg Niessing, and Heribert Meffert. 2006. "The Relative Strength of Affective Commitment in Securing Loyalty in Service Relationships." *Journal of Business Research* 59(12):1207–13. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2006.08.005.
- 24) F. Nunes, Paul, Joshua Bellin, Ivy Lee, and Olivier Schunck. 2013. "Converting the Nonstop Customer into a Loyal Customer." *Strategy & Leadership* 41(5):48–53. doi: 10.1108/SL-05-2013-0035.
- 25) Frydman, Smadar. 2022. "Attachment Styles Associations with Long-Term Relationships Mediated by Brand Loyalty in the Israeli Mobile Market." PhD, Universitat Jaume I, Castelló de la Plana.
- 26) Ganesh, Ashween. 2000. "Critical Evaluation of Low Ergonomics Risk Awareness among Early Product Development Stage of the Medical Device Industry." *Industrial Engineering Journal*.
- 27) Garson, Justin. 2016. *A Critical Overview of Biological Functions*. Cham: Springer International Publishing.

- 28) Grisaffe, Douglas B., and Hieu P. Nguyen. 2011. "Antecedents of Emotional Attachment to Brands." *Journal of Business Research* 64(10):1052–59. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2010.11.002.
- 29) Guenzi, Paolo, Laurent Georges, and Catherine Pardo. 2009. "The Impact of Strategic Account Managers' Behaviors on Relational Outcomes: An Empirical Study." *Industrial Marketing Management* 38(3):300–311. doi: 10.1016/j.indmarman.2007.09.011.
- 30) Hair, Joe F., Marko Sarstedt, Christian M. Ringle, and Jeannette A. Mena. 2012. "An Assessment of the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Marketing Research." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* 40(3):414–33. doi: 10.1007/s11747-011-0261-6.
- 31) Han, Heesup, Yunhi Kim, and Eui-Keun Kim. 2011. "Cognitive, Affective, Conative, and Action Loyalty: Testing the Impact of Inertia." *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 30(4):1008–19. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2011.03.006.
- 32) Helmig, Bernd, Jan-Alexander Huber, and Peter Leeflang. 2007. "Explaining Behavioural Intentions toward Co-Branded Products." *Journal of Marketing Management* 23(3–4):285–304. doi: 10.1362/026725707X196387.
- 33) Hock, Michael, and Christian M. Ringle. 2010. "Local Strategic Networks in the Software Industry: An Empirical Analysis of the Value Continuum." *International Journal of Knowledge Management Studies* 4(2):132. doi: 10.1504/IJKMS.2010.030789.
- 34) Hwang, Jinsoo, Ja Young (Jacey) Choe, Heather Markham Kim, and Jinkyung Jenny Kim. 2021. "Human Baristas and Robot Baristas: How Does Brand Experience Affect Brand Satisfaction, Brand Attitude, Brand Attachment, and Brand Loyalty?" *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 99:103050. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2021.103050.
- 35) Izogo, Ernest Emeka. 2015. "Determinants of Attitudinal Loyalty in Nigerian Telecom Service Sector: Does Commitment Play a Mediating Role?" *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* 23:107–17. doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2014.12.010.
- 36) Jacoby, Jacob, Robert W. Chestnut, and William A. Fisher. 1978. "A Behavioral Process Approach to Information Acquisition in Nondurable Purchasing." *JOURNAL OF MARKETING RESEARCH*.
- 37) Jaiswal, Anand K., and Rakesh Niraj. 2011. "Examining Mediating Role of Attitudinal Loyalty and Nonlinear Effects in Satisfaction-behavioral Intentions Relationship." *Journal of Services Marketing* 25(3):165–75. doi: 10.1108/08876041111129155.
- 38) Jewargi, Varun, Veerendrakumar M. Narasalagi, and Ummi Naiemah Saraih. 2022. "A Study on Brand Loyalty for Cosmetic Products among Female Customers in Belagavi City." 12(1).
- 39) Jiddi, Fatima Ezzahra. 2023. "Does Corporate Social Responsibility Result in Better Hotel Guest Attitudinal and Behavioral Loyalty?" *Heliyon* 9(8):e18669. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18669.
- 40) Kahn, Barbara E., Manohar U. Kalwani, and Donald G. Morrison. 1986. "Measuring Variety-Seeking and Reinforcement Behaviors Using Panel Data." *Journal Of Marketing Research*.
- 41) Kaur, Harsandaldeep, and Harmeem Soch. 2018. "Satisfaction, Trust and Loyalty: Investigating the Mediating Effects of Commitment, Switching Costs and Corporate Image." *Journal of Asia Business Studies* 12(4):361–80. doi: 10.1108/JABS-08-2015-0119.
- 42) Keller, Kevin Lane. 1993. "Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Managing Customer-Based Brand Equity."
- 43) Keller, Kevin Lane, and Donald R. Lehmann. 2006. "Brands and Branding: Research Findings and Future Priorities." *Marketing Science* 25(6):740–59. doi: 10.1287/mksc.1050.0153.
- 44) Kim, Long. 2024. "Understanding Customer Loyalty in Banking Industry: A Systematic Review and Meta Analysis."

- 45) Kriyantono, Rachmat. 2012. "Measuring a Company Reputation in a Crisis Situation: An Ethnography Approach on the Situational Crisis Communication Theory." 3(9).
- 46) Liu, Matthew Tingchi, IpKin Anthony Wong, Ting-Hsiang Tseng, Angela Wen-Yu Chang, and Ian Phau. 2017. "Applying Consumer-Based Brand Equity in Luxury Hotel Branding." *Journal of Business Research* 81:192–202. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.06.014.
- 47) Maheshwari, Vishwas, George Lodoros, and Siril Jacobsen. 2014. "Determinants of Brand Loyalty: A Study of the Experience-Commitment-Loyalty Constructs." *International Journal of Business Administration* 5(6):p13. doi: 10.5430/ijba.v5n6p13.
- 48) Mano, Haim, and Richard L. Oliver. 1993. "Assessing the Dimensionality and Structure of the Consumption Experience: Evaluation, Feeling, and Satisfaction." *Journal of Consumer Research* 20(3):451. doi: 10.1086/209361.
- 49) Martínez, Patricia, and Ignacio Rodríguez Del Bosque. 2013. "CSR and Customer Loyalty: The Roles of Trust, Customer Identification with the Company and Satisfaction." *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 35:89–99. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2013.05.009.
- 50) Morgan, Robert M., and Shelby D. Hunt. 1994. "The Commitment-Trust Theory of Relationship Marketing."
- 51) Mundt, Kerry, John Dawes, and Byron Sharp. 2006. "Can a Brand Outperform Competitors on Cross-category Loyalty? An Examination of Cross-selling Metrics in Two Financial Services Markets." *Journal of Consumer Marketing* 23(7):465–69. doi: 10.1108/07363760610713019.
- 52) Muzellec, Laurent, and Mary Lambkin. 2006. "Corporate Rebranding: Destroying, Transferring or Creating Brand Equity?" edited by J. M. T. Balmer. *European Journal of Marketing* 40(7/8):803–24. doi: 10.1108/03090560610670007.
- 53) Oliver, Richard L. 1999. "Whence Consumer Loyalty?"
- 54) Ringle, Christian M., Dirceu Da Silva, and Diógenes De Souza Bido. 2014. "Modelagem de Equações Estruturais Com Utilização Do Smartpls." *Revista Brasileira de Marketing* 13(2):56–73. doi: 10.5585/remark.v13i2.2717.
- 55) Roy, Subhadip, and Soumya Sarkar. 2015. "To Brand or to Rebrand: Investigating the Effects of Rebranding on Brand Equity and Consumer Attitudes." *Journal of Brand Management* 22(4):340–60. doi: 10.1057/bm.2015.21.
- 56) Rubio, Natalia, Nieves Villaseñor, and María Jesús Yagüe. 2017. "Creation of Consumer Loyalty and Trust in the Retailer through Store Brands: The Moderating Effect of Choice of Store Brand Name." *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* 34:358–68. doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2016.07.014.
- 57) Saini, Shivani, and Jagwinder Singh. 2020. "A Link Between Attitudinal and Behavioral Loyalty of Service Customers." *Business Perspectives and Research* 8(2):205–15. doi: 10.1177/2278533719887452.
- 58) Sarstedt, Marko, Joseph F. Hair, Jun-Hwa Cheah, Jan-Michael Becker, and Christian M. Ringle. 2019. "How to Specify, Estimate, and Validate Higher-Order Constructs in PLS-SEM." *Australasian Marketing Journal* 27(3):197–211. doi: 10.1016/j.ausmj.2019.05.003.
- 59) Shergill, G. S., and Bing Li. 2005. "Internet Banking—An Empirical Investigation of a Trust and Loyalty Model for New Zealand Banks." *Journal of Internet Commerce* 4(4):101–18. doi: 10.1300/J179v04n04_07.

- 60) Suhan, Mendon, Smitha Nayak, Raveendranath Nayak, Cristi Spulbar, Gokarna Vidya Bai, Ramona Birau, Lucian Claudiu Anghel, and Cristian Valeriu Stanciu. 2022. "Exploring the Sustainable Effect of Mediation Role of Brand Commitment and Brand Trust on Brand Loyalty: An Empirical Study." *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja* 35(1):6422–44. doi: 10.1080/1331677X.2022.2048202.
- 61) Tanford, Sarah. 2013. "The Impact of Tier Level on Attitudinal and Behavioral Loyalty of Hotel Reward Program Members." *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 34:285–94. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2013.04.006.
- 62) Techawachirakul, Monin. 2020. "Violence in Games May Not Promise an Effective Brand Strategy, but Plot Relation Does." *Journal of Promotion Management* 26(1):121–43. doi: 10.1080/10496491.2019.1685621.
- 63) Tellis, Gerard J. 2018. "Comments on 'Do Brands Compete or Co-Exist?'"
- 64) Wood, Lisa M. 2004. "Dimensions of Brand Purchasing Behaviour: Consumers in the 18-24 Age Group." 4.
- 65) www.forbes.com/sites/jemimamcevoy/2020/07/02/critics-slam-unilever-rebrand-of-fair--lovely-skin-lightener-as-glow--lovely/?sh=9a78074b7a65
- 66) www.hul.co.in/brands/beauty-wellbeing/glow-lovely/